

SHOULD GOVERNMENT OF FRANCE
SUBSIDIZE INNOVATION IN THE PRIVATE
SECTOR?

Survey of Literature Review

Both economists and decision-makers are interested in the relationship between public and private investment, which is still a contentious topic in macroeconomics. Whether government subsidies encourage or discourage business investment in R&D is a crucial subject. Additionally, it has a significant impact on how well they function, which in turn affects their long-term sustainability. The primary findings of current government subsidy research are summarized below. Although the initial objectives of government subsidy policies are to encourage business development and enhance business performance, deviations in policy implementation and execution frequently lead to policy misalignment and thus have multiple effects.

Governments frequently find themselves at a disadvantage when it comes to innovation, particularly when technological advancement puts consumer protection and market competitiveness to the test. However, governments do play a crucial part in the process. Through government-sponsored programs, they not only guide the development of new technology but also foster an innovative environment. In the midst of the most serious credit collapse when World War II, the Organization for economic cooperation and European Council issue nearly simultaneous policy statements to adopt the management strategy in order to improve research and innovation potential and, as a result, strengthen protracted growth in the economy.

Policy innovation refers to the development of new procedures, guidelines, techniques, and practices that allow governments to better achieve their objectives and address difficult issues. Agile governance is a modern example of creative policymaking. It is a set of strategies aimed at increasing the government's adaptability and flexibility as it responds to changing technological conditions. Public co-creation, experimentation, sandboxing, and outcome-based laws are examples of these methods. The game relationship between the government, the supported firm, and its rivals influences firms' innovation behavior and, as a result, innovation performance under various subsidy arrangements.

Businesses are among the most active microeconomic carriers and platforms for innovation, making them among the most significant forces behind the growth of a high-quality national economy (Greenstein, 2010; Aistleitner et al., 2021). Performance of industry innovation will directly be impacted by that of enterprise innovation (Li X. et al., 2021; Yin and Yu, 2022).

Businesses must therefore lead the way in industrial modernization. Government subsidies affect the market's capacity to make informed resource allocation decisions and are a crucial regulatory instrument for guiding high-quality economic growth (Wang et al., 2019).

While innovation is one of the driving forces behind growth, this level of government spending cannot be justified solely on the basis of innovation. These tools must also achieve their objective. Furthermore, from this vantage point, the findings of empirical studies examining R&D and innovation support mechanisms are quite inconsistent (Salies, 2018). Furthermore, there does not appear to be a direct relationship between the level of business investment in R&D and the generosity of states. In this regard, a straightforward comparison of Germany and France is illuminating and cannot be explained solely by sectorial differences.

Due to the importance of various types of market failures inherent in R&D activities, most countries have established public financial support systems that prioritize private R&D investment. (Montmartin and Massard, 2015). States have a variety of tools at their disposal, including tax incentives and subsidies being one of the best and most widely used. However, concerns about the effectiveness of such policy tools arise during a limited period of Public Finance.

Empirical Analysis

Regarding subsidies, after 2005, the implementation of ease of doing business pole regulations has resulted in new funding standards for initiatives where sectorial and regional plans predominate. This stimulated the growth of geographical incentives in total estimated public aid for corporate research and innovation, which is linked to the development of European regional legislation and emphasizes the importance of developing regional innovation and discovery strategies in the 2000-2021 initiative. Along with fostering residential R&D, the establishment of public-private partnerships and the encouragement of entrepreneurship and the growth of young, innovative businesses are the two primary goals of subsidy programs in France. National subsidies in France have historically been heavily concentrated and oriented at strategic actors and industries.

Fig.1. French government funding for private R&D from 2000 to 2021 (in percentages). Source: OECD DATA

As a result, beginning around 2006, the positive shift has been toward a rapid rise in the percentage of expenditures covered by payroll taxes. (graph one depicts a representation of these changes.). Quite specifically, from 2002 to 2004, TC accounts for 3% of DERD; from 2005 to 2008, it rises to 11%; and from 2009 to 2011, it is set at 22%.

Figure 2 demonstrates the geographic variation of private Innovation in thousands of Euro. Source: MENESR

Since we are concentrating on the spatial distribution of R&D activities and policies, we can see in Fig. 2 that there is a significant concentration of privately financed R&D investment in a small number of regions, which are accompanied by established zones with little corporate innovation funding. It should be noted that this configuration, which demonstrates a downward reliance

Table C.1
Serial correlation of residuals.

Test	Null hypothesis	Stat	p-Value
Born and Breitung. HR-test	no AR(1) process	-0.730	0.466
Born and Breitung. LM-test	no AR(1) process	0.200	0.843

Note: Linear Panel Model with FE by cross-section and time without spatial effects. Outlier controls are included.

Table C.2
LR test for heteroskedasticity.

Test	d.f.	Chi-2 stat	p-Value
LR-test	93	1389.18	0.000

Note: Linear Panel Model with FE by cross-section and time without spatial effects. Outlier controls are included.

Table C.3
Cross-section correlation.

Variable	CD-test		Abs (corr.)
	Statistic	p-Value	
$\ln(DERDF)$	35.70	0.000	0.359
residuals	3.37	0.001	0.315

Fig.3. Linear Panel Template with cross-section correlation. Source: OECD DATA

between adjacent nodes, is largely constant over the time span considered.

Two distinct first-order regression analysis tests in the error terms are shown in graph of C.1 (obtained after FE estimation). The first-order serial correlation is not found in any of the two Born and Breitung test iterations. Therefore, we draw the conclusion that the residuals do not exhibit first-order serial correlation.

An LR heteroskedasticity test is shown in Table C.2. This test contrasts GLS estimates for panels with heteroskedasticity with GLS estimates for homoscedasticity. In order for us to acknowledge the null hypothesis that does not exist, the completeness values of the two assumptions must be comparable, and the LR figure should be minimal. The results in graph of C.2 strongly contradict the null hypothesis that heteroskedasticity does not exist. As a result, in order to account for the existence of heteroskedasticity, we must adjust for the residuals' variance/covariance matrix.

Variable	Statistic	p-value	Abs (corr.)
Ln (DERDF)	35.70	0	0.359
Residuals	3.37	0.001	0.315

Fig.3. Gross-section correlation

The CD-Test results, which identify cross-sectional correlation, are shown in Fig. 3. The lack of cross-sectional association is the test's null hypothesis. The residuals resulting from a FE evaluation and our outcome variable were both subjected to the CD test. The null hypothesis of no cross-sectional overreliance is rejected by both tests. As a result, the FE estimator is unstable and ineffectual.

Policy Implications and Limitations

The majority of the French government's innovation strategies are resource tools. Immediate instruments include scholarships for academic and industrial experiments or for cooperative research projects under partnerships of both sides, awards targeted at helping SMEs advance their advanced technologies (together with repayable debts of small and mid-size enterprises and aids for technological partnership or research subcontracting), and subsidies for hiring researchers, doctoral students, or specialists for innovation activity.

The French government also provides tax break to promote the start-up and private equity industries, such as personal income tax breaks for investments in SMEs, wealth tax breaks and reductions for business perspectives, and capital gains tax breaks for stockholders or funds of funds established by the CDC. A research tax credit, a corporation's taxable income deduction for capital investments in R&D, directly applied for capital investments in scientific and technical research, and a tax exemption on patronage fees are examples of indirect instruments. The public has made supporting SMEs one of its top priorities since about the middle of 1990. Public support that is not reliant on R&D is used to fulfill these steps.

Many tools specifically designed for SMEs include co-financing and guarantee programs ease their access to financing (particularly through OSEO), etc. Meanwhile, initiatives to promote entrepreneurship have been launched, including the 1999 Regional Start-up Tournament and discount code programs (such as Entrepreneurs Clubs); advisory services and advice to encourage the creation of public rotational; or programs to make it easier to join the European and sectorial innovation systems.

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